

Features of Formal Style in Arabic Language

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Abstract:

Currently, there is a need to improve the official style used in international relations in accordance with the requirements of the time. Therefore, the study of the nature of formal communication is one of the important issues.

The specificity of each language is reflected in a certain way in official communication. For this, it is necessary to form the stylistics of the Arabic language and determine the place of the science of adulthood in the Arabic language.

This article describes in detail the syntactic and stylistic features of formal communication in modern Arabic.

Keywords: "stylistics" and "synchrony" diachrony, speech, terms, public newspaper, word-formation and syntactic levels.

INTRODUCTION

STYLISTICS (Greek *stylos* — writing, writing stick), stylistics, methodology — the study of language styles by linguistics, the essence and nature of the functional multi-layeredness of language from the point of view of synchrony and diachrony at the lexical-phraseological, phonetic, morphological, word-formation and syntactic levels. This is a network that studies the features of the literary language, describing the norms and methods of using the literary language in different language situations, in different types and genres of written literature, in different spheres of public life. The official style, which is considered the stylistics of official communication, that is, the methodology, is a standardized style of legal documents, the distinctive feature of which is that it is regulated, that is, subject to established procedures and restrictions.

Conducting research in the direction of the official text style requires, first of all, to pay attention to its vocabulary. It is known that words are the basis for understanding a text. A stylistic approach to a word creates the need to choose words that help clearly express a thought. The author's correct

choice of words is not only a sign of style, but also increases the value of conveying information in the text and enhances the effect of the content. Wrong choice of words makes it difficult to convey ideas and causes logical errors. In the official style, the vocabulary of documents is of particular importance. A distinctive feature of the language of documentary vocabulary is a high degree of determinacy, in which terms permeate a huge layer of nomenclature vocabulary. For example, the nomenclature of names: "Olimp", "Start", state acceptance commission, etc.;

The nomenclature of job titles in Uzbek and Arabic, widely used today, includes the following:

<i>sales manager</i>	مُدِيرُ مَبِيعَاتٍ
<i>Advertising manage</i>	مَدِيرُ الإِعْلَانَاتِ
<i>Director</i>	المَدِيرُ العَامِ
<i>Director of Commercial Affairs</i>	مَدِيرُ تِجَارِي

Product range: gasoline A-76, etc.

The language of official documents, in addition to legal, economic and legal-economic terms, uses sufficient technical terms:

<i>Energy current</i>	التَّيَارُ الكَهْرِبَائِي
<i>Sources of ionizing radiation</i>	مَصَادِرُ مِنَ الإِشْعَاعَاتِ المُوَيَّنَةِ
<i>Auxiliary equipment</i>	الوَسَائِلُ المَسَاعِدَةُ

Among them are many abbreviations in Uzbek, Russian and other languages. But Arabs do not use abbreviations well. In Arabic, an abbreviation is called اختصار, الاختصار, which means abbreviation. It is known that in Uzbek, an abbreviation is called an acronym. Arabs prefer to use the full name of the word. However, there are a small number of original Arabic abbreviations. The rest of the words considered abbreviations in another language are used as such in Arabic. For example:

UNESCO	اليونسكو ¹
(United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization)	
FAO	الفاو ²
(Food and Agricultural Organisation of the United Nations)	
ICARDA	الإيكاردا ³
(International Center for Agricultural Research in the Dry Areas.)	
GATT	الغات ⁴
(General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade)	

Full and Abbreviated Terms

OAPEC	الوابك
Organization of Arab Petroleum Exporting Countries	
مُنظَمَةُ الأَقْطَارِ العَرَبِيَّةِ المُصَدِّرَةِ للْبِتْرُولِ ⁵	

¹ http://siteresources.worldbank.org/TRANSLATIONSERVICESEXT/Resources/Translation_Style_Guide_Arabic.pdf

² http://siteresources.worldbank.org/TRANSLATIONSERVICESEXT/Resources/Translation_Style_Guide_Arabic.pdf

³ http://siteresources.worldbank.org/TRANSLATIONSERVICESEXT/Resources/Translation_Style_Guide_Arabic.pdf

⁴ http://siteresources.worldbank.org/TRANSLATIONSERVICESEXT/Resources/Translation_Style_Guide_Arabic.pdf

⁵ Maiburov N.A. Reading and translating an Arabic newspaper. –M.: 2003.-P.28

الاوليك OPEC

Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries⁶

مُنظَمَةُ الدُّولِ المُصَدِّرَةِ لِلبِتْرُولِ

Palestine Liberation Organization⁷ (م.ت.ف) منظمة التحرير الفلسطينية

NATO⁸ ناتو

ECO⁹ ايكو

We observe that the names of many news agencies appear in the press in the form of abbreviations. The most common of these are:

Associated Press (CPIA)¹⁰ [أ ب] اسوشيتيد بريس

ΦRG¹¹ [د ب أ] وكالة الصحافة الألمانية

France Press(Франция)¹² [ا ف ب] وكالة الصحافة الفرنسية

Reuters [ر] رويتر

Iraq Information Agency وكالة [و أ ع] انباء العراق

Iran Information Agency¹³ ارنا

Saudia Information Agency¹⁴ وكالة [و أ س] انباء السعودية

It is known that most of the terms used in military units come from foreign languages. Therefore, abbreviations of such terms are often used in military language. For example, some of them are:

FOBS ب ق م ج

Fractional orbital Bombardment Vehicles¹⁵ نظام القذف المدارى الجزئى

MIRV م ا د م

Multiple Independently Targeted Reentry Vehicles¹⁶ مركبات اعادة دخول متعددة

Also in official correspondence, dates, quantities and degrees are abbreviated.

Hijri م AD

history ك.م. kilometer¹⁷ ت

doctor¹⁸ (دكتور) د.

Saudi currency

ر.س (ريال سعودي)

Saudi Arabia م.س.ع (المملكة السعودية العربية)¹⁹

⁶ Ibid P.110.

⁷ http://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/Category:Arabic_abbreviations

⁸ Maiburov N.A. Reading and translating an Arabic newspaper. –M.: 2003. –P.178

⁹ Fateeva I.G. Work on Arabic press language.-T.: 2004. – P.70

¹⁰ Maiburov N.A. Reading and translating an Arabic newspaper. –M.: 2003. –P.176

¹¹ Maiburov N.A. Reading and translating an Arabic newspaper. –M.: 2003. –P.176

¹² Fateeva I.G. Work on Arabic press language.-T.: 2004. –P.3

¹³ Maiburov N.A. Reading and translating an Arabic newspaper. –M.: 2003. –P.176

¹⁴ . Fateeva I.G. Work on Arabic press language.-T.: 2004. –P.4

¹⁵ مجلة الدفاع الجرى. العدد الثالث. سبتمبر 1971. ص. 8

¹⁶ مجلة الدفاع الجرى. العدد الثالث. سبتمبر 1971. ص. 8

¹⁷ منجد

¹⁸ <http://www.unilang.org/viewtopic.php?f=25&t=8934>

Door (باب) ب

Page (صفحة) 20 ص

Etc (إلى آخره) 21 إلخ

Peace be upon him (صلى الله عليه وسلم) صلعم 22

At the end of a book, Arabs use the abbreviation هـ. Also, replace the mailbox with صندوق بريد. they mark it with letters and pronounce it as صاد باء.

It follows that each official working paper lexicon uses its own nomenclature, abbreviations and acronyms. Another formal-lexical feature of Arabic texts is the large number of nouns. Position, brand names are a clear example of this.

An address is a word or phrase addressed to a person. In Arabic, the use of the words ايها, ايته is strictly regulated.

As for the grammatical side of official documentation, the unification of the grammatical structure of the phrase and word form is considered to belong to the grammatical norms of the official style, representing the language of the documents. The selected option is fixed as a standard/example in each compositional part of the text. For example, in the Uzbek and Arabic text of the command in the heading of each item, indicate the addressee - "who?", and then "what should he do?" focuses on the answer to the question:

Syntax is a science that studies the rules of placement of endings and the function of each word in a sentence.

In written formal speech, preference is given to simple sentences. The peculiarity of simple sentences in the language of official business documents is that they convey information through a simple sentence equal to the amount of information communicated through a complex sentence in a document. At what cost is this achieved? Due to the length and semantic volume of a sentence without words.

Individual phrases can convey the same amount of information as a sentence.

Based on a bilateral agreement, it is possible to change the terms of the agreement, which is an integral part of this agreement.

بالتراضي قد تغيير شروط العقد أن تكون جزءاً لا يتجزأ من هذا الاتفاق

If a bilateral agreement is not reached...

إذا لم يتوصل اتفاق متبادل

If taxes are not paid within the specified period, the taxpayer will lose the right to apply for a loan again..

في حالة عدم دفع الضرائب المدة المحددة الحزم الدافع من حقوق إستلام القرض تكراراً

If taxes are not paid within the specified period..

...إذا لم تدفع الضرائب في المدة المعينة محددة

As can be seen from the examples, a phrase easily replaces a sentence and becomes a noun of an event. At the same time, such phrases not only condense information that takes up less space than a

¹⁹ Bodnar S.N. Arabic language/genre of commercial business papers and their linguistic specificity. - M.: Muravei. 2002. - P.55

²⁰ Ibid

²¹ <http://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/إلخ>

²² http://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/Category:Arabic_abbreviations

normal sentence, but also create a strict structure of phrases, one element of which is strongly dependent on another.

Payment is delayed... في حالة حدوث تأخير الدفع...

To make a decision... للإتخاذ القرار...

To make a quick decision... بهدف اتخاذ القرار في وقت عاجل...

They are an indivisible and necessary element of the phrase, justifying the action.

In addition to such phrases, a sentence in written speech in business style is often complicated by conjunctions, adverbs and adjectives. Thus, it stretches to a paragraph, and sometimes to a page, i.e. to several hundred words, especially in the case of orders, decisions, instructions, orders.

There are genres in which the text is equated to a sentence (memo, telegram, order, decision). A table is also a sentence with an isolated structure: the owner is constant information located on both sides, the participle is variable information located on vertical lines, which should be taken into account when translating written speech into oral speech.

The word order in a sentence in a formal style is distinguished by strictness and conservatism.

The names of the points acquire a logical, analytical character, which is emphasized in working texts (this is typical for the text organization of contracts, agreements, agreements).

Logical sequence as a unifier in the text of a document.

So/in this way وهكذا, besides that وعلاوة على ذلك, on one hand من ناحية, in other way أخرى من ناحية, in that reason عند ذلك من, also بما في ذلك, in this regard بالنظر إلى it is worth noting here من, conjunctions and introductory words, such as In the text of documents, demonstrative pronouns and adjectives are used as means of communication, replacing nomenclature names and terms in the text, listed among these المشار إليه, next القادم this هنا, هذه, جارٍ, last أخير, among تالي, included.

In addition to the above-mentioned peculiarity of formal compliance, they are united by a high level of genre standardization, covering all levels of language - lexical, morphological, syntactic and textual level. As a result, conservatism, isolation, a certain type of language is formed, which is closed to the manifestation of the individual style of the author and to the use of another style. The impersonality of the narration is expressed in the refusal to evaluate the event, interpretation, not to show emotional experiences. The formal style of speech has collected a huge number of speech phrases, templates, idioms, tested by many years of practice. The formula "typical situation - standardized style of speech" makes it possible to ensure the level of accuracy that distinguishes the document from any other paper, stipulating the use of standard tools.

Standardization facilitates the perception and processing of information contained in the document. Thus, the formal style and genres presented in official communication have a number of features. They indicate the level of language training of the person preparing the document.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that formal communication is a pressing issue of our time and occupies a leading position in all areas. The success of official negotiations and meetings is directly related to the culture of speech. It is also very important for an intelligent person to have information about the purpose of documents, their structure, the specificity of the expressions used in them and the place of use.

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